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Open Innovation in the Financial Sector: A Mixed-Methods Approach to Assess Bankers' Willingness to Embrace Open-AI ChatGPT

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ABSTRACT

As open innovation and Artificial Intelligence (AI) become more prevalent in financial institutions, early adoption of Chatbots will have a competitive advantage. However, ChatGPT is still less common in the financial sector than in other industries. This study attempts to understand bankers' perceptions towards using ChatGPT. Towards this, the study employed an exploratory sequential mixed-methods approach. Eventually, 10 bank professionals participated in the preliminary semi-structured interviews to gain insight into their perceptions. Sequentially, the study cross-sectionally examined the identified factors among 368 bankers to triangulate the framework with empirical evidence. The Thematic Content Analysis (TCA) analysis identified seven new factors related to bankers' use of ChatGPT, which were primarily validated in PLS-SEM assessments. The results showed the positive effect of performance expectancy, social influence, facilitating conditions, awareness, innovativeness, and system quality on ChatGPT usage and the negative effect of technology self-efficacy and IT features. Intriguingly, the moderating effects of central bank support were positively confirmed for innovativeness and social influence, but negative for the relationship between technology self-efficacy, awareness, and bankers' intention. This study offers a highly predictive model contemplating the applicability of an extended UTAUT model to explain the use of ChatGPT in the banking sector. Accordingly, we suggest that decision-makers should emphasize improving the individual attributes of their human capital towards technology and improving AI system quality, as well as working closely with government-powered authorities that would facilitate the diffusion process of AI Chatbots in the banking sector.

1. Introduction

Recently, the world has been experiencing unprecedented open

innovation advancements in modern technology as Artificial Intelligence (AI) keeps growing and advancing, which has sparked intense interest across industries (Sætra, 2023). With a plethora of innovations,

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intelligent Chatbot tools like Netomi.ai, ChatGPT, WP-Chatbot, Kore.ai, IBM Watson Assistant, Kasisto, Finn.ai, and Personetics demonstrate how significantly AI has progressed. As an AI-driven natural language processing tool, a Chatbot enables human-like discussions via text or aural means, such as responding to queries and helping with numerous tasks (Forbes, 2023). Chatbots can be built using multiple technologies, including natural language processing (NLP), machine learning, and rule-based systems (Open, 2023). They are typically deployed on messaging platforms, websites, mobile apps, or voice-based assistants.

In rapidly changing financial markets, data, information, and communication are paramount. AI Chatbots have revolutionized the financial market industry, including customer service, sales and marketing, support, information retrieval, and virtual assistants by providing solutions to some of its biggest challenges, improving efficiency, productivity, and streamlining various aspects of trading life cycle, from price discovery to trade reconciliation and automating tasks (Ali and Aysan, 2023). As technology becomes more prevalent in financial institutions, early adoption of AI Chatbots will result in a competitive advantage (Sætra, 2023).

When it comes to implementing cutting-edge technology to improve customer service and adhere to regulatory standards, the banking sector has frequently been at the vanguard (Bouteraa et al., 2024). Leveraging on the power of AI, ChatGPT applications analyze gigantic amounts of data in an accurate and timely manner, permitting commercial banks to leverage a broad range of advances. These include upgraded customer service (Koc et al., 2023), the handling of complex financial goals and decision-making, the potential to reduce costs, increased efficiency and productivity, as well as the streamlining of operations through automation (Bloomberg, 2023; Reuters, 2023). ChatGPT can also assist bankers in detecting suspicious patterns to prevent fraud, loan origination via the collection of customer data, assessing credit scores, evaluating risks, approving loan requests, providing personalized wealth management and planning services, which enable informed instant decision-making and ultimately lead to onboarding customer experience (Forbes, 2023; Reuters, 2023). Equally, AI Chatbots can contribute to the overall economy by creating new job opportunities, boosting efficiency, productivity, innovation and competitiveness of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) to sustain growth in a rapidly changing world economy (World Economic Forum, 2023).

The adoption of ChatGPT as an open innovation platform has increased significantly as a result of this technology's broad range of capabilities. At present, ChatGPT has over 100 million subscribers and receives over 1 billion visitors each month, representing a growth rate of 275% (Forbes, 2023; Reuters, 2023). Between December 2022 and February 2023, this growth in traffic and number of users had reached record-breaking heights. According to Research Nester (2023), the market for conversational AI systems would earn USD 333 billion by 2035, up from USD 140 billion in 2022, i.e., a projected 30% growth. The industry is expanding as a result of rising AI Chatbot and natural language processing adoption. ChatGPT is becoming increasingly practical across almost all industries globally, owing to the latest advancements in machine learning (Bloomberg, 2023). Given this context, recent statistics by Cornerstone Advisors (2023) showed an impressive increase in the usage of ChatGPT in banks and credit unions, i.e., from 4% to 13%. However, they remain less common in banking in comparison to other industries.

According to Rogers (1983), the technology diffusion process is essential for understanding potential users' readiness to embrace innovation and for ensuring the successful adoption of technology. Since the advent of open AI, the number of studies on ChatGPT has been increasing. As per the systematic literature review on ChatGPT by Alin et al. (2023), a considerable portion of the published articles investigated the tool's impact on education and academic scholarship; very few had attempted to explore ChatGPT adoption in the financial sector. Indeed, the majority of existing literatures on ChatGPT focus on academics and education (Bin-Nashwan et al., 2023; Frye, 2023; Gao et al.,

2023; Zhai, 2023), healthcare, medicine & biological sciences (Aydin and Karaarslan, 2023; Cahan and Treutlein, 2023; Mann, 2023), life coaching (Terblanche and Kidd, 2022), and law (Choi et al., 2023; Perlman, 2023), and other users of ChatGPT (Ma and Huo, 2023). On the other hand, there is restricted synthesis in developing appropriate testing frameworks for using ChatGPT in the context of banking and finance (Abu Bakkar et al., 2023).

There are frequent literature citations of the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) owing to its solid motivational basis in characterizing individual behaviour towards technology. Nonetheless, UTAUT has not been proposed in the new context of ChatGPT usage in banking. Furthermore, Bouteraa et al. (2024) highlighted that exploring individual, technological, and environmental attributes leads to the formation of a solid theoretical basis for understanding people's perceptions towards open innovation. Building on this, the current study originally conducted an exploratory investigation to understand bankers' perceptions of the usage of ChatGPT via the extension of the UTAUT model.

There are several ways in which this paper enriches the current body of literature. Firstly, it is one of the earliest attempts to identify the obstacles associated with ChatGPT usage in banking. Next, it utilizes and empirically validates the applicability of the UTAUT model to forecast bankers' acceptance of ChatGPT. Thirdly, the study employs the mixed method approach, i.e., integrating both qualitative and quantitative assessments. This analytical approach substantially aids in clarifying the complex interactions between the variables that affect the adoption of ChatGPT. Finally, the research conclusions offer novel insights to scholars and assist policymakers in developing effective strategies for fostering digital behaviour.

This paper has several sections. A summary of the theoretical background is given in Section 2. The research methodologies for the qualitative and quantitative phases are described in Section 3. The qualitative data analysis results are presented in Section 4, whilst Section 5 describes the final study model, the definition of constructs, and the hypotheses. Next, Section 6 presents the hypothesis testing and quantitative data analysis. Lastly, Section 7 offers insightful information regarding how bankers come to the decision to use ChatGPT.

2. Theoretical background

2.1. The Unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT)

Consumer behaviour has been broadly investigated in numerous socio-cultural settings utilizing prominent theoretical frameworks. Whilst prevailing frameworks have been employed, authenticated, revised, or panned, newer ones are progressing and being built to solve the faults/shortfalls in the former (Izuagbe et al., 2019). The original and variations of the TAM (TAM2 and TAM3), the Diffusion of Innovations Theory (DOI), the Social Cognitive Theory (SCT), and UTAUT are the most popular theories/models for studying the predispositions to embrace, implement, and utilize technology. The UTAUT model is considered the most advantageous (Shachak et al., 2019). With its high explanatory power and ability to predict, UTAUT has been determined to be the most comprehensive framework for describing technology diffusion (Souiden et al., 2020).

In order to provide a thorough framework for comprehending the intention and behaviour of users in relation to technology, the UTAUT model integrates eight main models/theories, namely the TRA (Theory of Reasoned Action), the TAM, MM (Motivation Model), TPB (Theory of Planned Behaviour, the combination of TBP and TAM, the PC utilization model, DOI, and SCT). Users' behavioural intention was identified to be directly impacted by performance expectancy, effort expectancy, and social influence, whilst actual behaviour was identified to be impacted by the construct of facilitating conditions. The UTAUT model outperformed the existing models by explaining 70% of the variance in technology acceptance. Since the function of ChatGPT is highly relevant

to elements of technology, it is rational to understand their use from the perspective of information systems research.

In a nutshell, the UTAUT model offers a robust and widely accepted framework for investigating the diffusion of open innovation, making it an accurate optimal for investigating the use of ChatGPT in the financial industry. Its comprehensive features, high predictive relevance, and adaptability make it an effective underpinning model for acquiring insights into the factors influencing open innovation, like AI-generative ChatGPT in the banking sector. On the other hand, while joining the use of ChatGPT into open innovation dynamics, it is necessary to consider the technical attributes like system quality, IT Features, data privacy, and the need for human oversight like usefulness, ease of use, social influence and facilitating conditions, especially in critical decision-making processes by getting formal approvals from relevant authorities like central bank. Overall, the integration of ChatGPT can complement and enhance various aspects of open innovation, making the collaborative innovation process more efficient, inclusive, and dynamic. Thus, UTAUT is used in this work as the underlying basis for investigating bankers' use of ChatGPT, offering insights into potential barriers and facilitators.

According to Souiden et al. (2020) in their systematic review, UTAUT has been proven to be applicable and reliable for analyzing how people embrace new IT systems in various domains and contexts, making it suitable for investigating the adoption of ChatGPT among bankers. Yet, the individual situations of users may limit the explanatory prowess of the model (Tarhini et al., 2016). Likewise, Venkatesh et al. (2012) recommended the integration of newfound contributing factors that could improve the prospects of the UTAUT in the users' context. Hence, this study primarily contributes to the extension of UTAUT via the addition of the new constructs, i.e., individual, technological, and contextual factors, apart from its replication in novel contexts. This creates a robust framework for explaining how bankers employ ChatGPT in a comprehensive manner.

3. Research methodology

The mixed-methods approach is widely used across various disciplines, including social sciences, education, health sciences, and business research. Utilizing the benefits of both qualitative and quantitative research whilst minimizing their weaknesses is the central goal of mixed methods research (Creswell and Creswell, 2018). By combining qualitative and quantitative data, researchers can gain deeper insights, cross-validate, verify, and triangulate findings, thereby providing a more robust and comprehensive analysis of the research problem (Creswell and Creswell, 2018; Sekaran and Bougie, 2019).

Hence, this current work employs the exploratory sequential mixed-methods design to investigate bankers' usage of ChatGPT. The investigation began with a review of the pertinent literature to gain a thorough understanding of the topic. The empirical investigation contained two sequential stages: Phase 1: the authors identified the empirical codes that are expected to form the research's foundation using information derived from the semi-structured interviews. From this, the main factors were developed, thus broadening the research's context. Subsequently, the hypothesis for each of the empirical codes was formulated to establish the ultimate research model. Phase 2: all the developed hypotheses were then tested via a quantitative cross-sectional survey involving a greater sample size so that the theoretical framework would be supported by stronger empirical evidence. The research methodology is further explained below.

3.1. Phase one: qualitative study

For the purpose of exploring the determinants of bankers' perception towards the usage of ChatGPT, a preface qualitative study was conducted involving bankers from various commercial banks who underwent open-ended semi-structured interviews. The inductive paradigm

was used to identify and categorize the factors derived from the interview transcripts. The conceptualized interpretations were organized in a hierarchy, with the top-level ideas serving as the primary constructs.

The main approach for acquiring data for this study was via focus groups. In this case, as advised by numerous qualitative researchers (Yin, 2017; Creswell and Poth, 2018; Creswell and Creswell, 2018; Sekaran and Bougie, 2019), a purposive sampling strategy was employed to choose pertinent informants who are experts on the phenomenon under study. In line with the study's goals and predetermined recognized components, i.e., the individual, technological, and environmental factors, the researchers devised an interview protocol. With regards to the qualitative sampling size, the subjective evaluation of the researchers determines the number of interviews when the saturation point is achieved, according to the majority of modern qualitative scholars (Yin, 2017; Creswell and Poth, 2018; Creswell and Creswell, 2018; Sekaran and Bougie, 2019). The investigator may cease the process after reaching saturation, i.e., when no new themes are being discovered and the data becomes redundant (Creswell and Poth, 2018; Sekaran and Bougie, 2019). A total of 10 informants took part in the semi-structured interviews, i.e., a sufficient number for this study to obtain saturation.

The transcribed data were analyzed using the qualitative computer program N.Vivo 14 for Thematic Content Analysis (TCA), which helped in locating the codes connected to the theoretical underpinning for the investigation. The authors followed Braun and Clarke's (2006) guidelines for conducting and recording an interview, listening to the recordings and subsequently transcribing them, verifying the transcripts and then coding them, naming and organizing the codes, inputting the quotations and memos into the right codes, scrutinizing and generating outputs, and ultimately putting the report into writing.

3.2. Phase two: quantitative study

The data derived from the semi-structured interviews were used to identify a number of probable determinants influencing the deployment of ChatGPT by bankers. The proposed final model was created using a series of hypotheses. Hypotheses testing was then carried out utilizing a quantitative cross-sectional survey involving a bigger sample of bankers from commercial banks. As suggested by Ringle et al. (2022), PLS-SEM in Smart PLS 4 was employed to validate the findings. According to Hair et al. (2002), PLS-SEM is regarded as a variance-based methodology that relies on least-squares functions and of which seeks to maximize the dependent variables' explained variance. Appropriate to PLS-SEM's suitability for theory development and for predicting or expanding a prevailing structural theory, it was hence used in this study.

The study created a survey to better understand the variables influencing bankers' adoption of ChatGPT. To ensure the instruments' validity, measuring scales employed in previous investigations were adapted to suit the research context. Each concept was measured using several items laid out on a 5-point Likert scale whereby (1) denotes "strongly disagree" and (5) denotes "strongly agree". Table 1 includes a list of the items and their sources. Positive results were derived from the pilot test involving 30 survey participants.

4. Phase one: qualitative data analysis and findings

4.1. Theoretical narrative

Seven new sub-themes were generated from the qualitative analysis in line with the three predetermined factors, namely awareness of the bankers, personal innovativeness, and technology self-efficacy, which represent the individual factors; IT features, time-saving features, as well as system quality, which denote the technological factors; and central bank support which denotes the environmental factor (Table 2). The study was validated by asking the field specialists to assess the patterns of the data in the derived themes. Using the informants' direct

Table 1
list of items and their sources.

Constructs	Description	No Items	Source
Behavioural Intention	Inclination to utilize technological innovations.	4	(Venkatesh et al., 2003)
Performance Expectancy	The system is beneficial and improves task performance.	4	(Venkatesh et al., 2003)
Effort Expectancy	Convenience and usability of the system.	4	(Venkatesh et al., 2003)
Social Influence	The opinions of certain parties influence an individual's system usage activities.	4	(Venkatesh et al., 2003)
Facilitating Conditions	Access to resources which facilitate the implementation of a specific technology.	4	(Venkatesh et al., 2003)
IT Features	IT features and information related to reliability, trustworthiness, security, privacy, and efficacy	5	(Sura et al., 2017)
System Quality	Entails the system's overall design, functionality, reliability, flexibility, and availability.	5	(Ahn et al., 2007; Delone and McLean, 2003)
Time-Saving Features	<i>Improving time efficiency, reducing the time needed to perform a task.</i>	4	(Iqbal et al., 2018)
Bankers' Awareness	Volume of information regarding a certain technology and the degree of awareness about its presence, idea, purpose, and advantages.	5	(Bouteraa et al., 2023)
Personal Innovativeness	Propensity and inclination to explore and test novel technologies.	4	(Agarwal and Prasad, 1998)
Technology Self-Efficacy	Users' perception of their capabilities to utilize a system for carrying out tasks and achieving intended outcomes.	5	(Compeau and Higgins, 1995)
Central Bank Support	The central bank's role in endorsing and driving technological usage and implementation.	4	(Amin et al., 2011)

Table 2
Summary of the Qualitative Study Output.

Themes	Sub-Themes Extracted	Participants										Total participants	Ratio (%)
		P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10		
Technology Determinants	IT Features	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	×	✓	×	×	07	70%
	System Quality	×	✓	✓	×	×	×	✓	✓	✓	×	05	50%
	Time-Saving Feature	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	×	✓	×	×	07	70%
Individual Determinants	Bankers' Awareness	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	×	×	08	80%
	Personal Innovativeness	✓	✓	✓	×	✓	×	✓	✓	✓	×	07	70%
	Technology Self-efficacy	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	×	×	×	×	✓	06	60%
Environment Determinants	Central Bank Support	✓	✓	×	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	×	✓	08	80%

quotes, the next sub-section summarises the results for each factor. This demonstrates the degree to which the findings fulfil the aim of the first phase.

The analysis of the interview transcripts uncovered that IT features are among the top technological factors affecting the phenomenon under study, as agreed by 70% of the informants. Their poor perceptions of various IT elements that typically assist bankers in performing tasks like security, trustworthiness, reliability, privacy, and efficacy stand as obstacles, making the adoption of ChatGPT an intimidating option. In addition, according to 50% of the informants, bankers focus more on the design (inclusivity) and flexibility of ChatGPT when carrying out various banking activities consistently and smoothly. Moreover, the mainstream of the informants (70%) frequently highlighted that bankers rely on the timing aspects. This implies that ChatGPT is an efficient, time-saving tool that can monitor the task schedule and assist in the accomplishment of tasks in a faster and more systematic manner.

The qualitative data revealed that awareness determines behaviour. The awareness of bankers is deemed a crucial personal aspect by 80% of the informants in determining whether or not they will adopt ChatGPT. Meanwhile, the biggest impediments are poor knowledge about the technology's concept, availability, significance, exitance, and advantages. Additionally, 70% of the informants emphasized their hesitance and unwillingness to experiment with new technology due to their lack of innovative attitude, reluctance to take risks, and desire to remain in their comfort zones. These personality traits may discourage bankers from adopting new technologies and utilizing unproven solutions because doing so would require them to disrupt their standard working procedures and expose them to the stress of failure. In addition, 60% of the informants remarked that bankers have downcast capabilities and master skills to use new technology-related platforms and ChatGPT to conduct their banking operational activities; thus, they perceive low technology self-efficacy.

The shortage of central bank support as a government-linked institution was identified as a fundamental environmental hindrance which was projected to impact the usage of ChatGPT in the banking sector. About 80% of the informants stressed that the central bank should set a favourable milieu and incentivize the application of technology. Hence, the adoption of financing technology services such as ChatGPT comes with the user expectation of receiving governmental aid such as subsidies, incentives, and policies.

5. Identification of constructs and hypothesis development

The final model was constructed using output from the qualitative data analysis. On top of the four primary constructs taken from UTAUT, another seven constructs (i.e., IT features, system quality, time-saving features, bankers' awareness, personal innovativeness, technology self-efficacy, and central bank support) were generically grouped as technological, individual, and environmental factors, which ultimately form the research model (see Figure 1). The sub-section below presents the hypothesized variables and their interrelationships.

5.1. Performance expectancy

There has been significant research focused on the construct of performance expectancy, i.e., the forecasting of users' perception regarding improvement in their tasks due to technology deployment. UTAUT (Venkatesh et al., 2003) and its extension of UTAUT2 (Venkatesh et al., 2012) deem performance expectancy as the primary indicator of behavioural intention. A number of studies highlighted this construct as crucial for elucidating the heightened usage of information systems (see Bouteraa et al., 2023; Bouteraa et al., 2022a; b; Osei et al., 2022; Tewari et al., 2023). Essentially, the degree to which ChatGPT fulfils the expectations of users is the only way to gauge practicality

Fig. 1. Research Framework.

(Sharma et al., 2022). The literature highlighted the importance of performance expectancy in determining user behaviour in using ChatGPT tools in various sectors, including travel and tourism (Melián-González et al., 2021), healthcare (Sitthipon, 2022), and life coaching (Terblanche and Kidd, 2022). However, less consideration has been given to investigating its role in the banking sector. In keeping with the literature, if bankers perceive that ChatGPT will contribute meaningfully towards enhancing their task performance and offer numerous benefits such as banking operation effectiveness, usefulness, as well as effortless and timely transactions, they may then be favourably disposed to use it. Therefore, this study hypothesizes that:

H1. : Performance Expectancy positively affects bankers' intention to use ChatGPT.

5.2. Effort expectancy

Effort expectancy crucially predicts the inclination of people to utilize technology. It is related to how a person sees a certain technology as easy and simple to utilize, i.e., without exerting much mental or physical effort (Venkatesh et al., 2003). In short, users have a higher inclination to utilize a technology deemed as simple (Venkatesh et al., 2012). Effort expectancy has been identified as a significant factor affecting behavioural intention (Bin-Nashwan, 2022; Rahim et al., 2022; Yeh et al., 2022). Building on this, individuals' effort expectancy would be essential in determining whether they would use ChatGPT. If ChatGPT is perceived to require little learning curve or time commitment, the intention to use the platform would be higher (Sitthipon, 2022). Accordingly, ChatGPT's convenience and ease of use can positively influence bankers' willingness to utilize them. The following is hence hypothesized:

H2. : Effort Expectancy positively affects bankers' intention to use ChatGPT.

5.3. Social influence

Social psychology theories promote social impact on behaviour. The conflict elaboration theories of social effect identified that adopting or rejecting an invention alters group interactions (Mugny et al., 1995). Kelman (1974) stated that compliance, internalization, and identification are the three most basic forms of influence. Various technology acceptance and usage models like the TRA, TBP, TAM, and UTAUT assert social influence as the effect of other people's views on technology usage (Venkatesh et al., 2003). Technology-related literature indicated that others' inducements, preferences, and expectations strongly influence users' behaviour (Al-Saedi et al., 2020; Bin-Nashwan, 2022; Bouteraa et al., 2021). Still, other investigations did not confirm this (Abbasi et al., 2021; Al-Hattami, 2023; Bouteraa et al., 2022a; b; Bouteraa et al., 2023). Conflicting findings showed that peer influence is situation-dependent, thus motivating this current study's context analysis. It could be construed that ChatGPT is trendy and modern, lending credence to the concept that bankers' usage of ChatGPT is influenced by their peers; hence, the following hypothesis.

H3. : Social Influence positively affects bankers' intention to use ChatGPT.

5.4. Facilitating conditions

This construct refers to the provision of the required technical resources for facilitating the deployment of a given technology (Venkatesh et al., 2012). The UTAUT model defines facilitating conditions as a reflection of the person's behavioural control (Venkatesh et al., 2008). Facilitating conditions have been emphasized in literature as a conditional element in the adoption of various technologies (Bouteraa et al., 2022a; b; Chekima et al., 2020; Palau-Saumell et al., 2019; Rahim et al., 2022). To navigate ChatGPT, users need access to technical support, straightforward interfaces, and helpful resources (Sitthipon, 2022). This suggests that the provision of adequate facilitating resources, including

technological know-how, internet access, and smart gadgets, on top of expert guidance and support, would help bankers have positive perceptions and ensure a seamless experience on the platform. This study hence hypothesizes that:

H4. : Facilitating Condition positively affects bankers' intention to use ChatGPT.

5.5. Internet technology (IT) features

With technological advances, banks have integrated Internet Technology (IT) into their banking operation activities and service delivery. IT features like security, privacy, trustworthiness, and reliability facilitate efficacy in performing banking operations performance. Hence, IT features of a possible application affect the technology's widespread acceptance (Abu Bakkar et al., 2023; Bin-Nashwan and Al-Daihani, 2021; Sura et al., 2017). With AI's power, ChatGPT applications can analyze gigantic amounts of data accurately, allowing bankers to leverage a broad range of operations and instantly advance through automation (Bloomberg, 2023; Reuters, 2023). Furthermore, a ChatGPT model trained on banking data would grasp financial terms, rules, and industry-specific nuances, benefiting bankers. This would enable more detailed and relevant responses to their queries. These features boost the acceptance of ChatGPT since most financiers are late adopters. Accordingly, the following hypothesis is conceptualized:

H5. : IT Features positively affect bankers' intention to use ChatGPT.

5.6. System quality

The initial D&M Information Systems Success Model (DeLone and McLean, 1992) and its 2003 updated form state that system quality should be strategic. Information production quality depends on a system's technical level. Typically, technology users demand system quality features like usability, availability, dependability, adaptability, and accessibility (DeLone and McLean, 2003). System quality is a crucial indicator of technology adoption (Bouteraa et al., 2023; Nguyen and Chen, 2023; Zhang et al., 2020). A system with high-quality features is more trusted by users and hence adopted. However, it is essential to note that system quality differs according to bankers' needs, preferences, and organizational requirements. Considering the convenient use and safe accessibility of the ChatGPT tool for bankers, along with its intelligent personalization features based on user preferences to perform various tasks efficiently and effectively, it is prospectively assumed to be reliable and would be adopted by bankers. Hence, the hypothesis below is proposed:

H6. : System Quality positively affects bankers' intention to use ChatGPT.

5.7. Time-saving feature

The influence of time on consumer behaviour is well acknowledged by behavioural economic theories (Becker, 1965). In a time-sensitive society, time is an indispensable intangible resource that can be exchanged for money or labour (Xu et al., 2019). The timeliness of service has constantly motivated consumers to employ technology (Hong et al., 2021; Ng et al., 2023; Yapp and Kataraiyan, 2022). The time-saving information processing and integration of AI ChatGPT into individuals' daily lives have increased the importance of punctuality for completing activities, increasing productivity, and achieving objectives (Tian et al., 2021). Its influence on bankers' behaviour has received scant research attention. ChatGPT can potentially save bankers' time through fast information access, routine automated tasks, efficient customer service, and training and onboarding (Tian et al., 2021). Therefore, financiers tend to utilize ChatGPT if this technology is perceived to save them time. From the relevant literature, the following

hypothesis is derived:

H7. : Time-Saving Feature positively affects bankers' intention to use ChatGPT.

5.8. Bankers awareness

Awareness is needed in the process of accepting innovation (Guilford and Donnelly, 1983). The rise in innovation is expected, along with the increase in technological knowledge (Rogers, 1995). When the public is adequately updated about a certain service, they will develop higher awareness and thus be driven to embrace it (Lujja et al., 2018). Higher awareness of a technology's benefits and limitations would improve its general acceptance (Pai and Alathur, 2019; Ratanya, 2017). Scholars have highlighted that awareness affects behavioural intention (Baabdullah, 2020; Flavian et al., 2020). Hence, individuals' awareness of the technology, its capabilities, and its potential uses can influence their intention to use it. The higher consciousness of ChatGPT and its availability, importance, existence, and benefits would form a positive perception and greater intention to use. Thus, increasing bankers' awareness of ChatGPT can be an effective way to increase adoption. This study hence hypothesizes that:

H8. : Banker Awareness positively affects bankers' intention to use ChatGPT.

5.9. Personal innovativeness

This construct was developed by Agarwal and Prasad (1998), indicating the tendency of a person to utilize a certain innovation. Personal innovativeness is crucial in the adoption of innovations (Abbasi et al., 2021; Bervell and Arkorful, 2020; Thakur et al., 2016). An individual's level of personal innovativeness determines how eager they are to try out novel activities (Ciftci et al., 2021). Therefore, innovative individuals who are open to new technologies tend to embrace ChatGPT. In contrast, less innovative individuals are more cautious about technological innovations and, hence, are less likely to adopt and use ChatGPT. Therefore, innovative tech needs to be marketed towards highly innovative individuals who are open to new technologies to maximize its adoption and usage among bankers. The following hypothesis is hence formed:

H9. : Personal Innovativeness positively affects bankers' intention to use ChatGPT.

5.10. Technology self-efficacy

This construct is a part of the social cognitive theory developed by Bandura (1989). It entails how a person perceives his capability to perform or accomplish specific tasks. Self-efficacy is subject- and situation-specific. Technology self-efficacy, therefore, refers to the confidence in achieving success and objectives using technology systems (Yoon et al., 2020). Self-regulation is related to an individual's motivation, achievement, emotion, cognition, and self-control (Bong and Skaalvik, 2003). Following the release of ChatGPT, technologists and practitioners have been intrigued and alarmed. In banking, ChatGPT could increase self-efficacy by providing confidence to bankers in effectively completing complex tasks and offering potent instruments that enhance their abilities (Bloomberg, 2023; Forbes, 2023; Reuters, 2023). Using ChatGPT in banking may reduce daily workloads, provide insights into performance progress, and facilitate communication between bankers and other stakeholders, including colleagues or internal departments, administration, and feedback mechanisms. However, not many studies have empirically examined the impact of self-efficacy on the utilization of ChatGPT, hence necessitating this investigation. Based on the earlier assertions, it can be stated as a formal hypothesis that:

H10. : Technology Self-Efficacy positively affects bankers' intention to

use ChatGPT.

5.11. Central bank support

Government support refers to administrative and financial assistance that helps introduce and implement new information technology (Torres et al., 2021). The credibility and reliability of a certain service can be improved with governmental support by driving technological applications in financial revolutions and investments in infrastructure. When governmental support is in place, the feeling of security is established (Hu et al., 2019). Empirical studies have proven the strong relationship between government support and technology adoption (Hu et al., 2019; Kreydenko et al., 2020; Stone et al., 2020). Using AI is a trending matter in the banking industry. However, this technology arms race also depends on central bank endorsement as a government-linked authority, making it easier and more reliable for users to accept the tool.

The functional conception is that central bank backing is necessary because using ChatGPT in banking is a two-edged sword. Governments can foster the development of AI standards and promote the interoperability of systems, which in the intervening time can be a significant barrier by either denying or hurdling the diffusion process. Thus, the central bank hangs in the balance as a decisive and conditional determining factor. As a related authority, the central bank can standardize interfaces and protocols to seamlessly integrate AI technologies into existing banking systems and promote the interoperability of various AI models or platforms. This can facilitate the adoption of ChatGPT by financial institutions, as they can more easily integrate it with their existing infrastructure. In light of the preceding, investigating central bank support as a moderating factor in using ChatGPT in the banking sector is necessary to develop meaningful insights. Although the integrity of government support as a valid moderating construct has been proven (Haleem et al., 2019; Li et al., 2020; Yoon et al., 2020), very few studies have explored its role as a moderator in the context of using ChatGPT. Consequently, the following hypotheses are developed.

H11. : Central bank support positively affects bankers' intention to use ChatGPT.

H12. : Central bank support has a positive moderation effect on the link between performance expectancy and the intention to utilize ChatGPT among bankers.

H13. : Central bank support has a positive moderation effect on the link between effort expectancy and the intention to utilize ChatGPT among bankers.

H14. : Central bank support has a positive moderation effect on the link between social influence and the intention to utilize ChatGPT among bankers.

H15. : Government support has a positive moderation effect on the link between facilitating conditions and the intention to utilize ChatGPT among bankers.

H16. : Central bank support has a positive moderation effect on the link between IT features and the intention to utilize ChatGPT among bankers.

H17. : Central bank support has a positive moderation effect on the link between system quality and the intention to utilize ChatGPT among bankers.

H18. : Central bank support has a positive moderation effect on the link between the time-saving feature and the intention to utilize ChatGPT among bankers.

H19. : Central bank support has a positive moderation effect on the link between awareness and the intention to utilize ChatGPT among bankers.

H20. : Central bank support has a positive moderation effect on the

link between personal innovativeness and the intention to utilize ChatGPT among bankers.

H21. : Central bank support has a positive moderation effect on the link between technology self-efficacy and the intention to utilize ChatGPT among bankers.

6. Phase two: quantitative data analysis and results

6.1. Sample of study

Missing values were assessed by performing descriptive statistics analysis; however, the results revealed none. Meanwhile, multivariate outliers were detected using the standard method of calculating the squared Mahala-Nobis distance at $p < .001$ for every case in the data set. Seven out of the 375 cases were identified as multivariate outliers, leading to their omission (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2013). Hence, 368 cases were valid for data analysis. Table 3 summarises the demographic statistics for the sample.

6.2. Measurement Model Assessment

This entails evaluations of the measurement model's reliability (composite reliability-CR), convergent validity (factor loadings and AVE or average variance extracted) and discriminant validity (Hetrotrait-Monotrait-HTMT) (Hair et al., 2019). Table 4 illustrates the retained item loadings for the model's assessment; they are shown to be substantially accepted as the items have reached the threshold values for factor loading (≤ 0.5), AVE (≤ 0.5), and CR (≤ 0.7). Two items (SI 4 and ITF 5) showed poor loading of less than 0.4; hence, they were removed as per Hair et al. (2018). Overall, the results confirm the validity of the measurement model.

HTMT ratios were used to assess discriminant validity (Kline, 2016). Table 5 shows that the HTMT values for all the constructs are 0.85 and below (Henseler et al., 2015); thus, no discriminant validity issues were identified. This led to the conclusion that the measurement model is valid.

6.3. Structural Model Assessment

As only a single source was utilized for the collection of data, Common Method Bias was tested first, as per Kock (2015), via full collinearity testing. Here, all the variables were regressed against a common variable; a $VIF \leq 5$ indicates no single-source bias. VIF values of 3.5 and below were yielded from the analysis, hence confirming the absence of single-source bias in the study's data (see Table 6).

The structural model analysis was used to test all the hypotheses.

Table 3 Demographic Information of the Study's Sample.

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	217	59%
	Female	151	41%
Age	18 to 40 yrs. Old	209	57%
	41 yrs. old and above	159	43%
Education level	College Diploma	58	15.7%
	First Degree (Bachelor's)	160	43.4%
	Postgraduate degree (Master's or PhD)	83	22.5%
	Professional certificate	62	16.8%
Job position level	Others	5	1.35%
	Clerks/Admin	149	40.4%
	Officer	97	26.3%
	Manager	76	20.6%
Overall experience in banking	Others	46	12.5%
	Junior: up to 5 yrs.	93	25.3%
	Medium: 6 to 9 yrs.	118	32%
	Senior: 10 yrs. and above	157	42.7%

Table 4
Summary Results of Convergent Validity and Reliability.

Constructs	Indicators	Loadings	CR	AVE
Intention	INT1	0.888	0.934	0.826
	INT2	0.895		
	INT3	0.947		
	INT4	0.904		
Performance Expectancy	PE1	0.837	0.906	0.708
	PE2	0.908		
	PE3	0.827		
	PE4	0.789		
Effort Expectancy	EE1	0.888	0.905	0.704
	EE2	0.795		
	EE3	0.786		
	EE4	0.882		
Facilitating Conditions	FC1	0.792	0.917	0.735
	FC2	0.870		
	FC3	0.884		
	FC4	0.882		
Social Influence	SI1	0.895	0.938	0.835
	SI2	0.921		
	SI3	0.925		
Personal Innovativeness	PI1	0.857	0.894	0.678
	PI2	0.746		
	PI3	0.812		
	PI4	0.873		
Bankers Awareness	AWA1	0.849	0.926	0.716
	AWA2	0.796		
	AWA3	0.893		
	AWA4	0.890		
	AWA5	0.800		
System Quality	SQ1	0.722	0.908	0.666
	SQ2	0.876		
	SQ3	0.795		
	SQ4	0.813		
	SQ5	0.863		
Technology self-efficacy	TSE1	0.923	0.939	0.756
	TSE 2	0.867		
	TSE 3	0.878		
	TSE 4	0.806		
	TSE 5	0.869		
IT Feature	ITF1	0.891	0.911	0.721
	ITF2	0.875		
	ITF3	0.853		
	ITF4	0.772		
Time-saving Feature	TSF1	0.840	0.920	0.742
	TSF 2	0.878		
	TSF 3	0.900		
	TSF 4	0.825		
Central Bank Support	CBS1	0.892	0.958	0.852
	CBS2	0.928		
	CBS3	0.950		
	CBS4	0.921		

Note: Items SI4 and ITF 5 have been removed due to poor loadings. All factor loadings are significant at $p < 0.05$.

Table 5
Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT).

	CBS	ITF	TSE	TSF	AWA	EE	FC	INT	PE	PI	SI	SQ
CBS												
ITF	0.372											
TSE	0.650	0.673										
TSF	0.249	0.626	0.516									
AWA	0.200	0.572	0.476	0.781								
EE	0.324	0.534	0.516	0.589	0.561							
FC	0.441	0.664	0.616	0.617	0.586	0.801						
INT	0.236	0.553	0.438	0.539	0.714	0.547	0.664					
PE	0.284	0.702	0.582	0.598	0.638	0.713	0.697	0.849				
PI	0.351	0.454	0.518	0.563	0.785	0.432	0.479	0.608	0.506			
SI	0.504	0.449	0.597	0.307	0.351	0.487	0.627	0.415	0.421	0.368		
SQ	0.447	0.847	0.709	0.685	0.651	0.666	0.710	0.653	0.733	0.539	0.499	

All values of HTMT ≤ 0.85 .

This study employed bootstrapping with 5000 iterations as per Hair et al. (2021) and Ringle et al. (2022). Table 7 presents the direct and moderating hypotheses testing results. An $R^2 = 75.2\%$ of the variance of behavioural intention was generated, fulfilling the criteria set by numerous academics (Shmueli et al., 2019; Hair et al., 2019; Hair et al., 2021).

As shown in Figure 2, social influence and usage intention are positively related, which is stronger at the high level of central bank support. Meanwhile, at the low level, it has no effect at all. This points to the importance of central bank support in strengthening the relationship. Furthermore, the positive link between personal innovativeness and usage intention is stronger at the high level of central bank support, while at the low level, it has no effect at all, as demonstrated in Figure 3. This again points to the importance of central bank support in strengthening the relationship.

The PLS predict was also examined to ensure the validity of predictive relevance. The case-level predictions were calculated whereby $k = 10$, as per Hair et al. (2019) and Shmueli et al. (2019). The results demonstrate that the Q^2 predict values are beyond zero ($Q^2 \text{ predict} > 0$), demonstrating the outperformance of the Linear Model (LM) benchmark by all the indicators. Hence, a comparative analysis between the RMSE values and the naïve LM benchmark could be made. The findings demonstrated that all the indicators produced smaller prediction errors than the LM ($\text{PLS-SEM} < \text{LM}$) (see Table 8).

7. Discussion and Conclusions

7.1. Meta-Inference

Meta-inference and the bridge technique were used together to create an agreement between the qualitative and quantitative analysis results for evaluation (Venkatesh et al., 2013; Venkatesh et al., 2016). The examination of the qualitative data showed that the bankers' awareness, technology self-efficacy, and individual innovation are

Table 6
Full Collinearity.

Variables	VIF
Intention to use	3.487
Perform Expectancy	3.555
Effort Expectancy	2.565
Social influence	1.759
Facilitate Condition	2.933
IT-Features	2.718
System Quality	3.404
Time-Saving Feature	2.460
Bankers Awareness	3.445
Personal Innovativeness	2.096
Technology Self-Efficacy	2.681
Central Bank Support	1.714

Table 7
Hypotheses Testing.

Hypothesis	Relationship	Std. Beta	Std. Dev	t-value	p-value	PCI LL	PCI UL	f ²	Decision
H1	Perform Expectancy → Intention	0.555	0.047	11.842	0.000	0.476	0.631	0.455	Supported
H2	Effort Expect → Intention	-0.182	0.051	3.562	0.000	-0.263	-0.096	0.048	Not Supported
H3	Social Influence → Intention	0.089	0.051	1.748	0.040	0.010	0.175	0.012	Supported
H4	Facilitating Condition → Intention	0.231	0.059	3.904	0.000	0.140	0.335	0.058	Supported
H5	IT-Features → Intention	-0.135	0.063	2.160	0.015	-0.241	-0.032	0.019	Not Supported
H6	System Quality → Intention	0.168	0.055	3.043	0.001	0.077	0.260	0.032	Supported
H7	Time-Saving Feature → Intention	-0.052	0.049	1.071	0.142	-0.134	0.026	0.004	Not Supported
H8	Awareness → Intention	0.319	0.056	5.742	0.000	0.230	0.412	0.115	Supported
H9	Personal Innovative → Intention	0.158	0.051	3.113	0.001	0.067	0.235	0.043	Supported
H10	Technology Self-Efficacy → Intention	-0.235	0.046	5.123	0.000	-0.309	-0.159	0.061	Not Supported
H11	Central Bank Support → Intention	0.062	0.048	1.280	0.201	-0.037	0.154	0.007	Not Supported
H12	Central Bank Support*Perform Expectancy → Intention	0.001	0.069	0.010	0.496	-0.097	0.131	0.000	Not Supported
H13	Central Bank Support*Effort Expect → Intention	0.107	0.077	1.390	0.082	-0.026	0.225	0.011	Not Supported
H14	Central Bank Support*Social Influence → Intention	0.090	0.040	2.270	0.012	0.034	0.166	0.024	Supported
H15	Central Bank Support*Facilitate Condition → Intention	-0.019	0.068	0.273	0.392	-0.137	0.087	0.000	Not Supported
H16	Central Bank Support*IT-Features → Intention	-0.032	0.086	0.377	0.353	-0.181	0.101	0.001	Not Supported
H17	Central Bank Support*System Quality → Intention	0.031	0.081	0.386	0.350	-0.084	0.184	0.001	Not Supported
H18	Central Bank Support*Time Saving Feature → Intention	-0.035	0.065	0.535	0.296	-0.161	0.046	0.002	Not Supported
H19	Central Bank Support*Awareness → Intention	-0.250	0.094	2.664	0.004	-0.384	-0.097	0.059	Not Supported
H20	Central Bank Support*Personal Innovative → Intention	0.128	0.067	1.900	0.029	0.013	0.232	0.020	Supported
H21	Central Bank Support*Technology Self-Efficacy → Intention	-0.095	0.052	1.810	0.035	-0.181	-0.016	0.016	Not Supported

Fig. 2. The moderating effect of central bank support on the Social Influence and Intention to Use relationship.

Fig. 3. The moderating effect of central bank support on Personal Innovativeness and Intention to Use relationship.

crucial personal traits that may improve their usage of ChatGPT. The qualitative findings also suggested that ChatGPT’s technological aspects, such as its IT features, time-saving features, and system quality, can act as hindrances. During the interviews, the informants also emphasized the importance of incentives, laws, and policies related to government and central banks as environmental barriers. The initial qualitative results were mostly supported by the quantitative data

analysis, which revealed that bankers’ intentions to use ChatGPT were highly influenced by awareness, personal ingenuity, technology self-efficacy, system quality, and IT features. However, the moderating role of central bank support was significant only for the links between awareness, technology self-efficacy, and social influence and intention.

Most of the qualitative results are generalizable via quantitative research, thus indicating the success of the mixed-method strategy in

Table 8
Q² Predict and the Predictive Performance of the PLS Model Vs. Benchmark. LM.

Indicators	Q ² predict	PLS-SEM_RMSE	LM_RMSE
INT1	0.522	0.680	0.592
INT2	0.449	0.660	0.555
INT3	0.672	0.537	0.489
INT4	0.618	0.560	0.503

Note: Intention = INT; Root Mean Squared Error = RMSE; Linear Model LM.

filling the gaps between qualitative and quantitative research and amalgamating the strengths of both methods. For further understanding of the study, the empirical results from the two research methods could be cross-referenced. Consequently, compared to a single-method approach, the mixed-methods research performed in this study gave profound insights into bankers' intention to deploy ChatGPT.

7.2. Discussion

Although open innovation tools like ChatGPT are promising and have the potential to permit commercial banks to leverage a broad range of advances, including upgraded customer service, handling of complex financial goals and decision making, the potential to reduce costs, increase efficiency and productivity, and streamline operations through automation (Bloomberg, 2023; Reuters, 2023), it is still early to understand if bankers could be reluctant to adopt such new technology for now. Thus, it is essential to conduct an exploratory investigation to understand bankers' perception towards using ChatGPT, i.e., via the extension of UTAUT by integrating the individual, technological, and environmental factors.

The study results show that the primary constructs of UTAUT are related significantly to bankers' intention to use ChatGPT. For instance, performance expectancy was found to strongly and positively impact bankers' intentions. This evidence confirms earlier research results carried out in different disciplines (Bouteraa et al., 2023; Bouteraa et al., 2022a; b; Osei et al., 2022; Tewari et al., 2023). From the result obtained, we could claim that when bankers perceive that open innovation (ChatGPT) can contribute meaningfully towards enhancing their task performance and offer numerous benefits, including banking operation effectiveness, usefulness, effortlessness, and timely transactions, they would have a higher inclination to utilize it. However, effort expectancy negatively affects bankers' intention to utilize AI ChatGPT. This indicates that the stronger the perceived effort among bankers in relation to ChatGPT, the lower their intention to adopt such a novel technology. This advocates that if a technology like ChatGPT is perceived as overly simplistic or lacking in features, it may lead to negative perceptions of its usefulness as users may question the capability of the technology in fulfilling their tasks or perceive it as too basic for their requirements.

The path analysis shows that social influence positively influences bankers' ChatGPT adoption intention. Some past studies reported a similar result (e.g., Al-Saedi et al., 2020; Bin-Nashwan, 2022; Bouteraa et al., 2021). In short, bankers tend to embrace ChatGPT if their social peers believe that such platforms deserve attention. By aligning individuals' behaviour with the expectations and practices of their social groups, positive social norms can significantly lead to the successful usage and deployment of technology. The research also found that bankers' intentions are shaped considerably by their facilitating conditions, which corresponds with literature from different contexts (Chakima et al., 2020; Palau-Saumell et al., 2019; Rahim et al., 2022). This implies that to navigate ChatGPT in the banking industry, bankers require access to technical support, straightforward interfaces, and helpful resources. By addressing barriers and creating favourable conditions, facilitating conditions enable bankers to overcome challenges and embrace the ChatGPT technology more readily. In general, the results indicate that UTAUT is applicable and has the explanatory power to address the issue in this study.

Unexpectedly, we found that IT features such as security, privacy, reliability, and trustworthiness negatively affect bankers' intention to use ChatGPT. Such a conclusion opposes studies from different contexts (Abu Bakkar et al., 2023; Bin-Nashwan and Al-Daihani, 2021; Sura et al., 2017). Since ChatGPT is still fairly new, there could be perceived risks among bankers in relation to security, reliability, trustworthiness, and privacy matters, in addition to a lack of digital literacy and skill requirements. This consequently has a negative effect on the adoption of such a novel innovation. Furthermore, there is a strong correlation between ChatGPT-related service quality and bankers' intention to adopt. The convenient use and safe accessibility of ChatGPT for bankers, along with intelligent personalization features based on user preferences to perform various tasks efficiently and effectively have led to the assumption that this technology is more prospective to be reliable and adopted by bankers. Accordingly, the output of the study implies that the technology features are crucial in explaining users' AI adoption.

The study also reveals that ChatGPT adoption intention was driven by bankers' awareness, which is consistent with the results of studies from various domains (Baabdullah, 2020; Flavian et al., 2020). This indicates that a higher consciousness of the concept of ChatGPT and their availability, importance, existence, benefits, and familiarity with ChatGPT interactions would form a positive perception and greater usage intention among bankers. The analysis also shows that the linkage between personal innovativeness and intention to use ChatGPT is statistically significant. Arguably, highly innovative people tend to be early adopters who embrace new technologies and influence others within their social networks to adopt ChatGPT. Hence, ChatGPT should be marketed towards highly innovative individuals who are open to new technologies in order to maximize their adoption and usage among bankers. However, instead of the expected positive effect, technology self-efficacy was found to negatively affect the intention to adopt ChatGPT. This means that AI could decrease self-efficacy by lowering bankers' confidence to effectively complete complex tasks and use potent instruments that enhance their abilities. This negative effect could be attributed to the bankers' perceived complexity as they may feel overwhelmed by the idea of interacting with a ChatGPT or believe that they lack the necessary skills or knowledge to effectively engage with the technology, which leads to the fear of failure to use ChatGPT correctly or the perception that this tool is uncontrollable.

With the inclusion of the moderating effect of central bank support, the research model emerges with some fascinating insights. First, the effect of social influence on bankers' ChatGPT adoption has become more assertive with different levels of government support. This implies that when related authorities, such as governments and central banks, standardize interfaces and protocols to seamlessly integrate AI technologies into existing banking systems and promote the interoperability of various AI models or platforms, society and other significant peers and partners in social networks can significantly foster the adoption of ChatGPT among bankers. Interestingly, bankers' innovativeness and their intention were found to be contingent on the level of central bank support in relation to ChatGPT implementation in the banking sector. When bankers perceive that governments foster the development of AI standards and promote the interoperability of AI systems, innovative individuals open to new technologies, such as ChatGPT tools, are more likely to adopt and use ChatGPT.

7.3. Theoretical Implication

There are several theoretical contributions of this study, particularly in the banking sector. First, the study affirms that the UTAUT model is applicable and can explain bankers' use of ChatGPT as an open innovation tool. Second, the study's framework extends the UTAUT model by including newly explored determinants that impact ChatGPT adoption in the banking sector. This expanded model considers individual, technological, and environmental determinants influencing bankers' intention to use ChatGPT. Third, the study's mixed-methods approach drives

the prevailing argument about the strengths and limitations of using quantitative and qualitative methods in research. By combining both methods, the study provides a more comprehensive understanding of bankers' perceptions towards ChatGPT. Ultimately, the study identified new factors affecting bankers' adoption of ChatGPT, including awareness, technology self-efficacy, personal innovativeness, IT features, time-saving features, system quality, and central bank support. These findings extend the prevailing literatures on technology adoption on top of strengthening the understanding of practitioners and researchers regarding the factors affecting ChatGPT adoption in the banking sector.

7.4. Practical Implications

The findings can be helpful for legislators, researchers, and bank management from a practical standpoint. They can be used as beneficial resources for creating efficient digital-oriented policies towards maximizing the benefits for customers, banks, and the national economy while pursuing digitalization. By offering a deeper explanation of the actual variables involved in bankers' usage of ChatGPT, the study provides a model for practitioners. To facilitate a smooth shift to open innovation, promote sustainability, and increase the competitiveness of banks, it thus provides a solid framework for creating policies and for planning and coordinating development initiatives.

The findings revealed several critical factors that can be leveraged to enhance the use of ChatGPT in the banking sector. To promote ChatGPT adoption intention among bankers, decision-makers should emphasize the potential performance improvements and benefits that bankers can derive from using the technology, i.e., by demonstrating the Chatbot's ability to enhance task performance, save time and effort, provide access to information, and offer personalized assistance. Moreover, organizations should focus on increasing awareness of AI technology among bankers by employing presentation strategies, educational campaigns, demonstrations, or testimonials. By focusing on improving system quality, banks can enhance bankers' perceptions of ChatGPT by investing in robust technical infrastructure, optimizing the user interface, ensuring reliable performance and responsiveness, addressing security concerns, and providing accessible support services. It is equally essential to consider bankers' self-efficacy and personal innovativeness by providing support and resources that enhance confidence in their abilities, such as clear instructions, user-friendly interfaces, tutorials, and responsive customer support. Finally, the central banks, as government-powered authorities, can facilitate the use of ChatGPT in banking by providing a supportive regulatory environment, promoting innovativeness, ensuring data privacy and security among users, and monitoring the implementation of ChatGPT technologies.

For banks and financial institutions that seek to stay competitive in the digital age, this study's findings provide practical suggestions. By adopting ChatGPT and leveraging the factors identified in this study, banks can improve customer service, reduce costs, and increase efficiency. Additionally, AI technology can help banks meet the growing demand for digital services. Finally, the study's results can also guide banks in designing and implementing innovative AI banking systems and products that meet customer needs and enhance competitiveness.

7.5. Limitations and Future Directions

Even with the intriguing findings, this research has its limitations. The utilization of a cross-sectional research design limits the study's capability to generate causal relationships and to identify changes over time. As variations in contexts and temporal factors may yield different outcomes, caution must be exercised when making generalizations. Therefore, further studies conducted in diverse settings and at various time points are recommended to enhance the ability to generalize the results. Additionally, the research focus was only on the banking sector in one country (Malaysia), which may limit generalizability to other industries or regions. Hence, further research is recommended to survey

other countries to examine the role of cultural differences and organizational factors. In addition, the research model can also be adopted for the purpose of studying new tools similar or alternative to ChatGPT, i.e., whether they are general or specific to the banking sector.

Ethical Statement/Approval

This research project does not involve the use of animal or human subjects and is therefore exempt from review under the Bioethics Act. The data collected and analyzed in this research were obtained solely from questionnaire sources, with explicit consent obtained from the participants and did not contain sensitive information. Therefore, the execution of this research did not necessitate any specific ethical approval.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Mohamed Bouteraa Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Project administration. Brahim Chekima Conceptualization, Software, Validation, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. Ramayah Thurasamy Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Resources, Supervision. Saeed Awadh Bin-Nashwan Validation, Data Curation, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision. Meshari Al-Daihani Validation, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Funding acquisition. Abderrahmane Baddou Validation, Writing - Review & Editing, Funding acquisition. Mouad Sadallah Validation, Data Curation, Writing - Review & Editing. Rudy Ansar Validation, Data Curation, Writing - Review & Editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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